

Decoding Depression: A Psycholinguistic Lexical Analysis of the Urdu Speech

Research Article

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Publication Details

Received: February 25, 2024 **Accepted:** March 25, 2024 **Published:** March 30, 2024

Abstract

Depression is one of the most prevalent mental health issues with a significant impact on both individuals and society. This study focuses on identifying linguistic markers of depression in the Urdu speech of Pakistani participants to aid in its early detection. Despite extensive research on linguistic markers of depression in various languages of the world, the Urdu language was still completely unexplored. This study addresses this notable gap by exploring and describing linguistic markers in the Urdu speech of Pakistani participants. Linguistic markers of depression can enable timely intervention by people around affected individuals and support mental health professionals in improving diagnosis and assessment. Additionally, they can aid developers of artificial intelligence in creating tools for automatic detection. This support is important for individuals who, due to internal loss of motivation or external negative social pressures, may not disclose their condition, seek medical help, and continue to suffer silently or even contemplate suicide. In this study, sixty Pakistani Punjabi-Urdu bilinguals, comprising an equal number of depressed and non-depressed participants, were selected using criterion sampling. Through semi-structured interviews, their speech was elicited, manually transcribed, and analysed for both context-independent and

context-dependent lexical markers. The analysis revealed significant differences in the use of absolutist, negative emotion, positive emotion, cognitive, religious, and health-related words between the two groups.

Keywords: linguistic markers of depression, the Urdu language, lexical analysis, Urdu content words, language of depression, automatic detection

1. Introduction

Depression is a major mental health issue affecting millions around the world (World Health Organization, 2023). Unfortunately, many affected individuals keep suffering in silence due to stigma and lack of motivation to seek help (American Psychiatric Association, 2022; Comer, 2017; Gotlib & Hammen, 2010). The tendency deprives them of valuable support from their social circle and mental health facilities (Khawaja, 2013; Maisel, 2011; Watts, 2018). It causes them to lose productivity, puts their health, relationships and careers at stake and even leads many of them to contemplate suicide (Kvarnstrom, 2017; Slonim, 2014; World Health Organization, 2023). The loss of productivity not only impacts the individual but also imposes a significant socioeconomic burden on their family and society (Kvarnstrom, 2017; Slonim, 2014; World Health Organization, 2020).

One tentative solution to the problem is the discovery of such objective indicators of depression that can help people around affected individuals take notice and provide timely help (Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018; Slonim, 2014; Stirman & Pennebaker, 2001). A family member or close friend cannot (and should not) diagnose depression, but at least, they can take the person to a mental health professional for evaluation and support. Despite advances in medical and psychological research, there remains a need for accessible, objective and non-invasive methods to identify depression (Barch et al., 2019; Comer, 2017; DeRubeis & Strunk, 2017; Nutt, 2008; Weissman et al., 2020). Linguistic analysis offers a promising avenue for this (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Slonim, 2014; Tausczik & Pennebaker, 2010). Linguistic markers can be readily available to anybody around an affected individual completely free (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Slonim, 2014; Tausczik & Pennebaker, 2010). Moreover, they can help mental health professionals first improve diagnosis and then better assess the effectiveness of the treatment (Gumus et al., 2023; Nook et al., 2022). It can significantly reduce their reliance on the self-report which often tends to understate or overstate facts (Palmieri & Stern, 2009; Sarwar et al., 2022). Additionally, artificial intelligence can also be employed to automatically detect and report depression through the analysis of text and speech produced on electronic gadgets (Coello-Guilarte et al., 2019; Deshpande & Rao, 2017).

Luckily, psycholinguistic research in pursuit of depression-specific changes in the linguistic behaviour of depressed individuals has shown some promising results (Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018; Boyd & Schwartz, 2021). For example, studies have revealed that the word choices of depressed and non-depressed people are significantly different (Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018; Boyd & Schwartz, 2021). Depressed people tend to use more first-person singular pronouns (Rude

et al., 2004; Stirman & Pennebaker, 2001), negative emotion words (Ramirez-Esparza et al., 2008; Rude et al., 2004), absolutist words (Adam-Troian & Arciszewski, 2020; Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018) and cognitive words (Liu et al., 2020; Papageorgiou & Siegle, 2003). These findings are well-substantiated but not yet conclusive (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021). Until more studies are conducted, especially cross-linguistic and cross-cultural ones, and the results become consistent across all studies, they cannot be regarded as diagnostically reliable (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Slonim, 2014; Trifu et al., 2017). Cross-linguistic and cross-cultural studies can confirm that it is depression, not cultural factors, that causes specific linguistic changes in the behaviour of depressed people (Huang & Wong, 2014; Matsumoto & Yoo, 2006). Moreover, if such a study is conducted in Urdu, it can extend the scope of service to well over 231 million people (Maldonado Garcia, 2016, 2018), or even over 841 million people if Hindi speakers are also included (Emery, 2023; Zeidan, 2023). However, there is still a notable gap in studies, leaving the Urdu language largely unexplored.

Given the identified gaps, this study aims to conduct a qualitative, comparative lexical analysis of the Urdu speech of depressed and non-depressed Pakistani participants, focusing on context-dependent and context-independent content words to identify objective linguistic markers of depression. Although function words (e.g. pronouns) also have an enormous potential to indicate depression (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Tausczik & Pennebaker, 2010), they are not directly noticeable and cannot be measured without the involvement of special equipment, software and technical expertise. Therefore, this study was delimited to only those content words (e.g. adjectives) that can be noticed with the naked eye. (However, it will further need to be determined whether these lexical choices are precisely noticeable to the naked eye or their detection should be limited to technical analysis only.) As the Urdu language was going to be investigated for the first time, we decided to make our pursuit qualitative so that none of the related semantic word categories was missed out. (A discovered difference might not readily find a theoretical explanation but it could still be valuable for further investigation.) Moreover, taking into account the fact that computer-assisted, automatic coding of the words had considerable chances of error (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021), it was also decided that each word would be coded manually while carefully taking its context into account. Other quality and rigour considerations included the collection of fresh data of high psychometric specificity (instead of using *in situ* or *language-luggage* data) and the analysis of the speech data (instead of written texts because speech is more natural, spontaneous and ubiquitous).

The research questions that this study endeavoured to answer were: (1) Do depressed and non-depressed Pakistani Urdu speakers choose content words differently? (2) If yes, what are those differences, (3) which of those differences are significant, (4) whether those differences are context-dependent or context-independent and (5) whether these differences correspond cross-linguistically to the findings of the previous studies. The fourth question was important with regard to assessing the role of a machine in automatically detecting depression.

2. Literature Review

Language has long been a subject of intrigue for researchers, and recent psycholinguistic studies have made significant strides in understanding its link to mental health, particularly depression (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Tausczik & Pennebaker, 2010). Acknowledging the contributions of earlier researchers such as Beck (1967b), Stone (1966), Bucci and Freedman (1981), Pyszczynski and Greenberg (1987), Hart (1984) and Weintraub (1981) etc., the 1990s was the period when the *Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count* (LIWC) was developed by American psychologist James Whiting Pennebaker and his colleagues (Tausczik & Pennebaker, 2010). It was the first computer program that made automated text analysis objective, transparent and convenient (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Tausczik & Pennebaker, 2010). Although other tools have been developed and recent advancements in artificial intelligence also show promise, LIWC remains the most preferred tool for psycholinguistic lexical analysis (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Pennebaker et al., 2022). Using the same program, Stirman and Pennebaker (2001) conducted a comparative analysis of the works of depressed and suicidal poets (e.g. Sylvia Plath) and non-depressed, non-suicidal poets (e.g. Robert Lowell) to make a ground-breaking discovery that the former poets had used significantly more self-referential language. The link between increased use of first-person singular pronouns and depression was also confirmed by several other researchers including Mehl et al. (2001), Rude et al. (2004), Lisa Fast and David Funder (2010), Fernández-Cabana et al. (2013), Pulverman et al. (2015) and Leis et al. (2020). However, some researchers such as Rodriguez et al. (2010), Jarrold et al. (2011) and Sonnenschein et al. (2018) failed to replicate this result.

Another important finding that was made using LIWC was the increased use of negative emotion words. Rude et al. (2004) conducted a lexical analysis of the essays of depressed, formerly depressed and non-depressed college students to discover that there was a positive correlation between the use of negative emotion words and depression. This finding was replicated by several other researchers including Ramirez-Esparza et al. (2008), Vanheule et al. (2009), Sohn (2017) and Leis et al. (2019). The studies that found an inverse correlation between depression and the use of positive emotion words include those conducted by Baikie et al. (2006), Rodriguez et al. (2010), Bernard et al. (2016), Sørensen (2015) and Sohn (2017).

The most notable recent work that established a link between depression and increased use of absolutist words is that of Al-Mosaiwi and Johnstone (2018). Al-Mosaiwi and Johnstone (2018) developed a LIWC dictionary of English absolutist expressions and conducted the LIWC analysis of huge textual data of posts made at different internet forums by more than 64000 members. The comparative analysis of the data of test and control groups revealed that depression group members had used 50% more absolutist words than control group members and the absolutist words were better indicators of the severity of depression than negative emotion words. However, the frequency of absolutist words was still high in the depression recovery forums (possibly as a result of the scar hypothesis) (Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018; Lewinsohn et al., 1981). The finding was replicated in another study by Adam-Troian and Arciszewski (2020) as well. This study was also

conducted on a large data that had been collected from *Google Trends*. The studies that failed to replicate this finding include those by Cohen (2019) and Yahya and Rahim (2023), possibly due to relatively smaller sample sizes and completely different research designs. Cohen (2019) analysed three-paragraph essays of university students whereas Yahya and Rahim (2023) analysed tweets of Twitter users.

Depressed individuals have also been found to use considerably more cognitive words (Liu et al., 2020; Papageorgiou & Siegle, 2003; Slonim, 2014). Using a portable audio recorder, Mehl et al. (2001) recorded naturalistic sound bites of depressed participants for two to four days. The LIWC analysis of the transcriptions revealed that depressed participants had used significantly more cognitive words, especially such causation words as *since*, *because* and *how* etc. Similarly, Rodriguez et al. (2010) found the prevalence of cognitive words in the personal diaries and online blog writings of depressed individuals, especially such mechanism words (e.g. *get*), causation words (e.g. *how*), insight words (e.g. *realize*) and inhibition words (e.g. *avoid*). Other researchers who confirmed this finding include Grisham et al. (2011) and Denson et al. (2012) whereas a study by Vanheule et al. (2009) could not replicate this finding. Vanheule et al. (2009) conducted a two-hour-long, semi-structured interview with 32 Dutch outpatients and the analysis of the transcription did not reveal any correlation between depression and the use of cognitive words.

Despite these advancements, there remains a need for further investigation into cross-linguistic and cross-cultural variations in linguistic markers of depression, particularly in under-researched languages like Urdu. Given the identified gaps, this study aims to conduct a comparative lexical analysis of Urdu speech among depressed and non-depressed Pakistani participants, focusing on context-dependent and independent content words to identify objective linguistic markers of depression.

3. Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Underpinnings

The theoretical foundation of this study is based on the relationship between depression and language, mirroring the connection between mind and behaviour (Bloom et al., 2006; Carroll, 2007; Kagan, 2017). This relationship is grounded in the understanding that internal mental processes influencing depressive affect manifest themselves in linguistic behaviour (Bloom et al., 2006; Carroll, 2007; Kagan, 2017) Emotion reactivity, emotion regulation and cognition are three processes known to cause changes in linguistic behaviour (Aldao, 2013; Rottenberg et al., 2005; Slonim, 2014; Stirman & Pennebaker, 2001).

Impaired emotion reactivity is the key feature of a depressive disorder (Comer, 2017; DeRubeis & Strunk, 2017). Depression potentiates reactions to negative stimuli, attenuates reactions to positive stimuli, and sometimes causes insensitivity to emotional stimuli regardless of their valence. (Bernard et al., 2016; Rodriguez et al., 2010; Rottenberg et al., 2005; Slonim, 2014). Studies have

shown that positive attenuation can reduce positive emotion words in the speech of affected people, negative potentiation can increase negative emotion words and their speech may become devoid of both kinds of emotional words due to emotional insensitivity (that is also referred to as emotion context insensitivity) (Bernard et al., 2016; Rodriguez et al., 2010; Rottenberg et al., 2005; Slonim, 2014). Depressed people become insensitive to external emotional stimuli because their attention becomes focused on the self (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Pyszczynski & Greenberg, 1987; Slonim, 2014). This may be the reason that their speech is marked with more reference to the self and less reference to the others (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Slonim, 2014; Stirman & Pennebaker, 2001).

Depression is also marked by the inability to regulate emotions effectively (Aldao, 2013; Bylsma et al., 2008; Rottenberg et al., 2005; Slonim, 2014). As a poor emotion regulation strategy, depressed people try to resolve their distress through excessive thinking about the causes and consequences of disturbing events (Aldao, 2013; Bylsma et al., 2008; Rottenberg et al., 2005; Slonim, 2014). Such thinking finds expression in the language of depressed people through cognitive words (Denson et al., 2012; Papageorgiou & Siegle, 2003; Tackman et al., 2018).

Another key feature of depression is impaired cognition (Beck, 1967a; Beck et al., 1983; Davey, 1994; Thomas & Altareb, 2012). Depressed people cannot think as clearly and logically as non-depressed people can (Beck, 1967a; Beck et al., 1983; Davey, 1994; Thomas & Altareb, 2012). Depressed people find it hard to make meaning because their mind fails to process complexities, grasp details and nuances and connect dots coherently (Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018; Prange-Morgan, 2021). Therefore, they tend to oversimplify, overgeneralize and exaggerate facts, on the one hand, and show cognitive inflexibility and obstinacy, on the other (Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018; Beck et al., 1983; Slonim, 2014). Increased use of absolutist words in speech may be a manifestation of this tendency (Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018; Prange-Morgan, 2021).

3.2 The Speech Elicitation Instrument

The participants' speech was elicited using emotional, memory retrieval, and rumination stimuli to stimulate depression-specific mental processes (i.e., emotion reactivity, emotion regulation, and meaning-making). The brief semi-structured interview was adapted from the emotions interview developed and validated by Rottenberg et al. (2005). The instrument was capable of generating depression-specific idiographic speech content without being inquisitive or insensitive to the privacy and well-being of the interviewees (Kidwell et al., 2010; Rottenberg & Vaughan, 2008; Slonim, 2014; Vanderlind et al., 2020). The adapted, translated version was reviewed and pilot-tested before administration. The interview asked the participants to recall and describe in detail any one of the happiest and any one of the saddest events of their life. Two additional, warm-up questions were added before the main questions of the interview on the recommendation of the consulting psychiatrists of the patients. One was about COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan (*Do you think the pandemic is real or is it a carefully crafted hoax?*) and the other was about bullying and ragging at Pakistani colleges and universities (*How can bullying and ragging of the juniors by their seniors at*

colleges and universities be prevented?) These questions were added because at the time of this study, both questions were talk of the town (Saleem, 2020; Sharaz, 2019).

3.3 The Sample

This study employed a sample of 60 participants, consisting of thirty depressed and thirty non-depressed Pakistani Punjabi-Urdu bilinguals. The participants' speech was elicited through a semi-structured interview, translated and reviewed for accuracy, and analysed for depression-specific linguistic markers. Although a smaller sample size in a qualitative study can also produce valuable insights (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011; Gast, 2010), a bigger sample size was selected for more meaningful inferential statistics (Dutka & Hanson, 1989; Forsyth, 2017; Tufféry, 2011). There was an equal number of men and women in both groups. All participants belonged to the urban areas of two major cities of the Punjab province of Pakistan: Lahore and Gujranwala. All participants were adults (aged between 21 and 60 years) and represented various strata of society. Depressed participants were selected at three different private clinics by clinical psychologists and psychiatrists through the criterion sampling technique. The patients with acute, non-comorbid major depressive disorder were selected excluding those that had suicidal ideation or were critically acute. Non-depressed participants were selected by making a one-to-one correspondence with their depressed counterparts based on their gender, age, qualification, area, profession, socio-economic background and marital status. Each non-depressed participant needed not to have a personal or family history of any mental disorder as well as those physical illnesses that can cause symptoms of depression. The selection of non-depressed participants was made with the assistance of clinical psychologists and general physicians.

3.4 The Collection of Data

After formal greetings and the exchange of initial background particulars, the researchers asked one of the two warm-up questions. This initial part assisted the participants in feeling comfortable and becoming fluent in conversation. The initial question was followed by the main questions of the interview. The interviews took about twenty minutes average time (the shortest being eleven minutes long and the longest being thirty-seven minutes long). Each interview was audio recorded and manually transcribed in the Roman script. The transcription was carefully proofread (while repeatedly listening to the recordings) three times (in three different sessions). The process was carried out so meticulously that it took four months to complete.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured that the sampling and the data collection were in strict compliance with the ethical principles of the Belmont Report (1979) and the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki (2013). To start, each participant was only suggested to participate in the research after the approval of a clinical psychologist and a psychiatrist (both). This ensured that only patients

who could safely do so participated in the interviews. Critically acute patients or those with suicidal ideation were excluded as a precaution.

Then, the consulting psychiatrist explained to the participants that the interviews were voluntary. The researchers ensured that none of the participants felt obliged to do so. Extreme care is evident in the fact that out of the 337 patients who were initially suggested to participate, only 233 approached the researchers to obtain detailed information, and out of these 233 patients, only 74 gave their written consent to participate. The interview process was completed only with 39 patients. Out of these 18 female and 21 male patients, 15 male and 15 female patients were finally selected because they better fit the selection criteria than others. In the case of non-depressed participants, 80 people were approached and only 55 of them provided written consent. Out of 19 women and 27 men who met the selection criteria, 15 women and 15 men were finally made part of the sample.

In addition, the researchers first discussed the purpose, objectives, and methodology of the research verbally with each patient, also openly explaining the advantages, disadvantages, and risks of participation (while also being careful that the issue of social desirability bias may not arise). After the patients had understood everything well, they were requested to also read the consent form, and formally sign it. The attendants accompanying the patients were also made part of the process. No interview or audio recording took place until the participant had assented to it completely freely, comfortably, and knowingly. Further, after each interview, the participant was sent back to the consulting psychiatrist for post-interview evaluation and professional support (if needed, but none of the participants engaged in that option as they felt they did not need it).

Then, after the patients' interviews had been recorded, the audio recordings were transferred to a personal computer, and the files were deleted from the smartphone, and securely overwritten to protect the privacy and confidentiality of the participants. The files that were saved on the computer were given numbers instead of names and kept in an encrypted drive. Moreover, the initial part of the interview in which the participant had shared his/her personal background information, was removed from the recording, as well as the transcription. After that, it was carefully evaluated and thoroughly discussed whether there were any conflicts of interest and none was found. To conclude, the protocols were documented and formally submitted to the concerned research ethics committee for consideration and approval.

3.6 The Analysis of Data

Each word of the speech of depressed and non-depressed participants was manually coded for analysis while reading the transcribed text and listening to the recording. Apart from reading the text and situating the word in its context, the recording was also listened to, for taking nuances of the spoken language into account. In this way, the exact connotation of each word was carefully ascertained and a semantic label was assigned to it in an MS Excel spreadsheet. Such an arduous and time-consuming task of manually coding a huge data of the speech of 60 participants was

undertaken to do justice to the first qualitative study of the Urdu language. If automatic text analysis performed on such well-supported languages as English was only about 80% reliable and researchers recommended that the results should cautiously be interpreted accordingly (Boyd & Schwartz, 2021; Pennebaker et al., 2022; Tausczik & Pennebaker, 2010), performing automatic text analysis on such an unsupported (or poorly supported) language as Urdu could not have been a good idea at all.

In many cases, the text was not segmented into words but phrases. For example, the sentence “Yad nahi parta ke khushi ka lamha kabhi aya ho” (*I do not remember that I have ever been happy*) was segmented into three phrases instead of five isolated (content) words: “Yad nahi parta” (*I do not remember*), *khushi ka lamha* (*the moment of happiness; a happy event*), *kabhi aya ho* (*ever came*). Separate words in phrases “yad nahi parta” (*I cannot/do not remember*), “khushi ka lamha” (*the moment of happiness*) and “kabhi aya ho” (*ever came*) do not convey what the speaker has intended in the sentence nor will the listener perceive them separately. It is the phrases that convey what the speaker is referring to and what the listener will perceive.

Moreover, breaking down these phrases into isolated words could also cause misleading counts of different labels. For example, as isolated words, one positive emotion word “khushi” and one cognitive word “lamha” would be added to two different categories whereas as a phrase, only one count would be added to the category of positive emotion words. (Please note, however, that the phrase was actually counted as a negative emotion word because if the context is taken into account, the speaker has intended neither the positive emotion word nor a cognitive word in the phrase but rather a negative emotion of sadness and dejection.)

Similarly, “aya ho” is a function word in the phrase “kabhi aya ho” but if it is separated, it will become a content word and we will have to be counted as a cognitive word. Please note that Urdu words often need postpositions and auxiliaries to complete their form. “Yad parna” is one such example given above. “Yad” (*memory*) is a noun whereas “yad parna” (*recall*) is a verb. Therefore, in semantic terms, “yad parna” needs to be counted as one word, not two words.

Besides the context-dependent coding, the context-independent coding was also done based on each word’s most common use in the Urdu language. For example, in the example sentence given above, the word “khushi” was also counted as a positive emotion word. The context-independent analysis was performed to compare its results with those of the context-dependent analysis to see whether the two types of analyses could indicate depression the same way or differently.

Before running statistical analyses, the segmentation and coding of the text were reviewed and micro-edited four times. The process had to be repeated the third time because minor corrections were still required in the second round and it was repeated the fourth time for quality and rigour considerations. The descriptive statistics was performed on the data in the MS Excel program and the inferential statistics was performed in the IBS SPSS program.

4. Results and Discussion

This study's context-independent, qualitative lexical analysis identified 42 different semantic categories in the speech of thirty depressed and thirty non-depressed participants, highlighting the significant linguistic differences that can aid in the diagnosis and understanding of depression. However, the number of 35 of them was too small to be considerable for drawing any meaningful comparison. For example, there were only 17 instances (0.12% of the total speech) of death-related words (e.g., *mar jana*; *die*) in the speech of depressed participants, while non-depressed participants made such references only 10 times (0.07%). Similarly, there were words expressing confusion and uncertainty (e.g. *bokhlahat*; *confusion*), words used to make contrast (e.g. *faraq*; *difference*) and words denoting perception (e.g. *daikha*; *saw*). These words were used for a total of just 47 times (0.34%), 75 times (0.54%) and 113 times (0.82%) by the depressed participants respectively and 28 times (0.19%), 90 times (0.60%) and 153 times (1.02%) by the non-depressed participants. The seven sizeable semantic categories included words referring to negative emotion, positive emotion, cognitive processes, absolutism, relationships, health, and religion. The difference between depressed and non-depressed participants was statistically significant in 5 of these categories and insignificant in 2. It was the number of relationship words and the positive emotion words that did not differ significantly between depressed and non-depressed participants. While previous studies have shown some differences in linguistic markers between depressed and non-depressed individuals, this study provides a detailed, context-specific analysis, identifying key semantic categories with significant differences. (Please see the following table for the *t*-test group statistics for all seven sizeable semantic categories).

Table 1. The Independent Samples T-Test Group Statistics

Categories	Participants	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Absolutist Words	Depressed Participants	30	2.34	0.85	0.15
	Non-depressed Participants	30	1.35	0.53	0.1
Positive Emotion Words	Depressed Participants	30	4.1	2.15	0.39
	Non-depressed Participants	30	4.86	2.39	0.44
Negative Emotion Words	Depressed Participants	30	5.97	2.28	0.42
	Non-depressed Participants	30	3.71	1.42	0.26
Cognitive Words	Depressed Participants	30	16.46	4.35	0.79
	Non-depressed Participants	30	13.31	3.08	0.56
Religious Words	Depressed Participants	30	0.82	0.88	0.16
	Non-depressed Participants	30	1.6	1.62	0.3
Health Words	Depressed Participants	30	1.88	1.43	0.26

Relationship Words	Non-depressed Participants	30	0.09	0.18	0.03
	Depressed Participants	30	2.87	1.87	0.34
	Non-depressed Participants	30	3.23	2.46	0.45

The results of the independent samples *t*-test indicated significant differences between depressed and non-depressed participants in the use of words signifying absolutism, negative affect, cognitive processes, health, and religion. However, there were no significant differences in the use of words signifying positive affect and relationships. (To control the family-wise error rate (FWER), the *p*-values were adjusted and compared with the adjusted thresholds first using the Bonferroni method and then also using a more powerful, Benjamini-Hochberg procedure.) The effect sizes of difference in the use of negative emotion words, absolutist words, cognitive words and health words were large whereas they were medium in the use of religious words.

Table 2: The Independent Samples T-Test

		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
							Lower	Upper
Absolutist Words	Equal variances assumed	5.4	58	<0.001	0.98	0.18	0.62	1.35
	Equal variances not assumed	5.4	48.7	<0.001	0.98	0.18	0.62	1.35
Positive Emotion Words	Equal variances assumed	-1.3	58	0.2	-0.76	0.59	-1.93	0.41
	Equal variances not assumed	-1.3	57.36	0.2	-0.76	0.59	-1.93	0.41
Negative Emotion Words	Equal variances assumed	4.6	58	<0.001	2.25	0.49	1.27	3.23
	Equal variances not assumed	4.6	48.52	<0.001	2.25	0.49	1.27	3.23
Cognitive Words	Equal variances assumed	3.24	58	<0.001	3.15	0.97	1.21	5.1
	Equal variances not assumed	3.24	52.21	<0.001	3.15	0.97	1.2	5.11
Religious Words	Equal variances assumed	-2.29	58	0.03	-0.77	0.34	-1.45	-0.1
	Equal variances not assumed	-2.29	44.81	0.03	-0.77	0.34	-1.45	-0.09
Health Words	Equal variances assumed	6.78	58	<0.001	1.79	0.26	1.26	2.31

	Equal variances not assumed	6.78	29.93	<0.001	1.79	0.26	1.25	2.32
Relationship	Equal variances assumed	-0.63	58	0.53	-0.36	0.56	-1.48	0.77
Words	Equal variances not assumed	-0.63	54.09	0.53	-0.36	0.56	-1.49	0.78

In the context-independent (CI) analysis, the absolutist words were found to be higher in the speech of depressed participants not only collectively but in pairwise comparison as well. Except for just 3 depressed participants, the rest of the 27 participants used considerably more absolutist words than did their corresponding counterparts. The most prevalent Urdu absolutist words found in the speech of the participants were *hamaisha* (always), *intihai* (extremely), *hargiz* (at all), *beshumar* (countless), *namumkin* (impossible), *sab/sabhi* (all), *yaksar* (altogether), *har banda/har koi/saray hi* (everyone), *kabhi nahi* (never), *mukammal tor par* (completely) and *sara/sari/saray* (all; entirely; totally). The findings of this study have important implications for both clinical practice and future research. The higher use of absolutist words among depressed participants suggests a potential linguistic marker for depression, which could be utilized in diagnostic tools and therapeutic interventions.

In the context-dependent (CD) analysis, absolutism became increasingly prominent in the speech of depressed participants whereas it was almost nowhere found in the speech of non-depressed participants. Although the non-depressed participants had used generic absolutist words on many occasions, the expressions rarely reflected cognitive inflexibility. For example, the sentence “ham sab nay ikathay bas karwa li thi” (*We all had one whole bus booked together*) contains absolutist words but does not reflect absolutist thinking whereas the sentence “mujhe sirf aik hi rasta nazar ata hai, aur koi rasta ab mumkin nahi raha” (*There is only one option left, no other option is anymore possible now*) is clearly reflecting absolutist thinking without employing explicit absolutist words. In 21 (9 female and 12 male) depressed participants, absolutist thinking was highly noticeable, in 5 others (3 female and 2 male depressed participants), it was moderately noticeable and in 1 (female) participant, it was mildly noticeable. Three (2 female and 1 male) depressed participants, however, did not make any such impression (although these participants had still used a few (3 to 5) absolutist words in their speech). On the other hand, just 2 female participants made mild to moderate impression of absolute thinking and the rest of 28 non-depressed participants did not make any such impression although 9 of them had used 10 to 16 absolutist words in their speech. The three non-depressed participants who had used more absolutist words than their depressed counterparts did not make an impression of absolutism. One of these three depressed participants (who had used fewer absolutist words) made a strong impression of absolutism while the other two made a mild impression.

The most prevalent Urdu words in the category of negative emotion words were *dukhi* (dejected), *udhas* (sad), *sar par sawar* (rumination), *nuqsan* (loss), *khamyan* (flaws), *masla* (problem), *tenshan*

(tension), *bura/buri/buray* (bad), *afsos* (remorse), *manfi* (negative), *aziyat* (agony), *ghalati* (mistake), *ulti/ultay* (evil; disturbing), *bechaini* (anxiety), *mushkil* (trouble), *paraishani* (worry) and *takleef* (pain). In CI analysis, the depressed participants collectively used about double negative emotion words (5.80% on average) than non-depressed participants (3.69%), and in pairwise comparison, 7 non-depressed participants used more negative emotion words than the depressed counterparts (5 non-depressed participants produced considerably higher and 2 non-depressed participants produced slightly higher figures). In CD analysis, the average increased to 7.54% in the depressed participants and decreased to 2.11% in the participants of the other group, and the individual values of all 30 depressed participants became bigger than those of the non-depressed participants. All 30 depressed participants made an impression of negative potentiation and none of the non-depressed participants made such an impression. This impression was strong in the speech of as many as 27 depressed participants and it was moderate among the rest four. None of the 7 non-depressed participants who had used more negative emotion words (according to the CI analysis) made even a mild impression of negative potentiation.

In the CI analysis, positive emotion words were used 4.07% and 4.85% by the depressed and non-depressed participants. The difference was not only apparently marginal but statistically insignificant as well (with a *p*-value of 0.199 and a *t*-value of -1.299 in the independent samples *t*-test). In the pairwise comparison, 13 depressed participants rather used more positive emotion words than their non-depressed counterparts (e.g. 3.9% as compared to 2.79% or even 7.99% as compared to 5.07%). The most prevalent Urdu positive emotion words included *khushi/khush* (happiness/happy), *acha/achi/achay* (good), *acha laga* (liked it), *hosla afza/hosla afzai* (encouraging/enouncement), *musbat* (positive), *behtar/behtari* (better/improvement), *shukar* (gratitude), *aitmad* (confidence), *maza* (enjoyment), *hansna/hansi* (laugh/laughter), *asan* (easy), *haseen/payara/payari* (beautiful), *shadi* (wedding) and *umeed* (hope). In the CD analysis, the average number of positive emotion words increased to 6.10% in the speech of non-depressed participants and decreased to 2.33% in the speech of depressed participants and the difference became statistically significant (with the *t* value of -8.464, the *p*-value of <.001 and large effect size in the independent samples *t*-test). None of the non-depressed participants gave even a mild impression of positive attenuation and all 30 depressed participants gave a moderate to high impression of positive attenuation (the impression was moderate among 4 depressed participants).

The most prevalent Urdu cognitive words included *soch kar/sochna/socha/sochti thi* (different forms of 'think'), *khayal* (thought; guess), *maana/maan'na/man liya* (different forms of 'believe'), *chahta/chahti/chahna* (different forms of 'want'), *waja* (reason; cause), *jaanta/jaanti/jaan'na* (different forms of 'know'), *halanke* (whereas), *shayad* (perhaps), *chahye* (should), *kiyunke/chunke* (because), *asar* (effect), *nateeja* (consequence) and *ho sakta hai* (maybe). The descriptive and inferential statistics of cognitive words were similar in both types of analyses. On average, depressed participants used 16.46% and 17.21% cognitive words and non-depressed participants used significantly fewer 13.31% and 11.43% cognitive words. Although 8 non-depressed participants used slightly more cognitive words than the depressed counterparts, in most cases, the number was

substantially high in the speech of depressed participants (e.g. 26.23% as compared to 11.72% and 17.83% as compared to 11.06%).

The most prevalent Urdu relationship words included *ammi/amma/maan/walida* (different words for ‘mother’), *abbu/walid/baap/payo/baba* (different words for ‘father’), *bivi* (wife), *shohar/mian/in ke abbu* (different words for ‘husband’), *gharwale* (family members), *dost/doston/friends/sahailiyan* (different words for ‘friend’), *maan-baap/walidain* (different words for ‘parents’), *shadi* (wedding), *bache/beta/beti/bete/betiyan* (different words for ‘children’), *bhai/bhaiyon* (brothers), *behan/behnain/behnon* (sisters), *susral* (in-laws), *daadi* (grandmother) and *kazan* (cousins). The descriptive and inferential statistics of the relationship words were similar in both types of analyses. The relationship words were marked and counted from three different angles: all relationship words in general, the relationship words that indicated a healthy relationship (e.g. *nahi, husband* (sic) *to mera bohat khayal rakhte hain*; my husband is really nice and caring) and the relationship words that indicated a strained relationship (e.g. *bare bhai bohat zayadati karte hain*; I am being wronged by my elder brother). In all three categories, the difference was statistically insignificant with *p*-values of 0.53, 0.25 and 0.47 respectively (in the independent samples *t*-test).

The analysis produced two unexpected findings too: the health words and the religious words. Although they were not asked about their health during the interview directly or indirectly, the depressed participants made frequent references to health (243 times) and they were mostly about their own health issues and concerns. On the other hand, the non-depressed participants rarely made any reference to their own health and the references to the health of the other people were not many either (there were just 15 such instances). The descriptive and inferential statistics in both types of analyses were similar in this category. The most frequent Urdu health words in the speech of the participants included *kharab tabiat/tabiat theek nahi* (feeling unwell), *dawai* (medicine), *hasptal* (hospital) *beemar/beemari* (ill/illness), *blood pressure* (hypertension), *sugar* (diabetes), *sorh* (burning sensation), *dabao* (stress), *disturb* (disturbed), *bigarti/bigar gai/kharab ho gai* (different words for ‘worsen’), *theek ho gaya/gai/gaye* (got well), *hamla* (attack), *dard* (pain), *sehat* (health), *nabz* (pulse), *dil ki dharkan* (heart beat) and *check-up* (medical examination).

As far as religious words are concerned, the researchers were expecting that depressed people would have used more religious words than non-depressed participants but the picture was quite the opposite. Ten depressed participants did not use even a single religious word, sixteen depressed participants used just a few of them and the remaining four used only 8 – 12 such words. In total, there were 109 religious words in the speech of depressed participants (in the context-independent analysis). On the other hand, as many as 27 depressed participants directly used religious words. The CI analysis found 240 religious words and the CD analysis increased this count to 263. Please note that only those words were added to this category that were used in the religious denotation or connotation (e.g. *dua*; prayer), not those that were used only as customary expressions (*Alhamdulillah*; thank God). For example, the words “Allah” in “Allah ne bacha liya” (*Allah protected me*) and “dua” in “main mun se kuch nahi kehti, bas dil main Allah se dua karti hun” (*I*

silently pray to Allah in my heart) are religious words whereas the words “Ma-sha-Allah” in “beti ki ab ma-sha-Allah shadi ho gai hai” (*my daughter is now married ma-sha-Allah*) and “Alhamdulillah” in “Ab nahi hota Alhamdulillah” (*Now, I am all right Alhamdulillah*) are cultural, colloquial or customary expressions. The difference in the use of religious words was also statistically significant (with a p -value of 0.03).

5. Conclusion

This study conducted an in-depth, qualitative, psycholinguistic, lexical analysis of hand-coded Urdu speech from depressed and non-depressed participants, revealing significant differences in several semantic categories. Statistically significant differences were found in the use of absolutist words, negative emotion words, cognitive words, religious words and health words. These differences were significant in both context-independent and context-dependent analyses. The context-independent analysis did not find any significant difference in the use of positive emotion words; however, the difference was significant in the context-dependent analysis, according to which, the depressed participants had used fewer positive emotion words than their counterparts. In response to the research questions, the results of the study indicate that depressed and non-depressed Pakistani Urdu speakers use content words differently; these differences can be noted in many semantic categories, especially the ones aforementioned, and Urdu dictionaries for automatic text analysis can also (and should) be developed so that artificial intelligence can be involved in automatically detecting depression among Urdu speakers as well.

Furthermore, four significant findings of the study corresponded with previous cross-linguistic research: increased use of absolutist words (e.g. Adam-Troian & Arciszewski, 2020; Al-Mosaiwi & Johnstone, 2018), negative emotion words (e.g. Leis et al., 2019; Rude et al., 2004) and cognitive words (e.g. Grisham et al., 2011; Rodriguez et al., 2010). This correspondence supports the hypothesis that depression-specific changes in linguistic behaviour are universally caused by internal mental processes and not by external cultural factors, and therefore, language has the potential to indicate depression objectively. However, the case with the use of positive emotion words was mixed. Similar use of positive emotion words by depressed and non-depressed participants, as per the CI analysis, corresponded with the finding of the study by Rude et al. (2004) whereas the decreased use of positive emotion words by depressed participants, as per the CD analysis, corresponded with the findings of the studies by Baikie et al. (2006) and Bernard et al. (2016) etc. The differences in the use of health words and religious words were new findings and sought attention for further investigation and theoretical explanation.

While previous studies have shown some differences in linguistic markers between depressed and non-depressed individuals, this study provides a detailed, context-specific analysis, identifying key semantic categories with significant differences. The findings of this study have important implications for both clinical practice and future research. For example, the higher use of absolutist

words among depressed participants suggests a potential linguistic marker for depression, which could be utilized in diagnostic tools and therapeutic interventions.

Despite these findings, there remain gaps in the literature that warrant further investigation, particularly regarding the context-independent versus context-dependent use of emotion words. Future research should focus on several areas: the significance of absolutist, negative emotion, cognitive, health, and religious words in both context-dependent and context-independent analyses, the disparity in context-independence of negative versus positive emotion words, and the exploration of Urdu function words as potential indicators of depression.

We hope that this first qualitative, psycholinguistic exploration of the Urdu language will prove a good stepping stone to achieving the ultimate goal of effectively managing depression, saving precious lives and ensuring the well-being of not only Pakistani Urdu speakers but also the speakers of other languages in the world.

Funding: This study was not funded in any shape or form by any party.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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